

Commodifying Breast Cancer Awareness: A Hypermodal Study of Selected Pakistani Advocacy Advertisements

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Abstract

This article aims to study the linguistic choices of Pakistani breast cancer advocacy advertisements. In Pakistan, the situation of the prevalence of this ailment is worse, and due to such situation, various campaigns are being run with the collaboration of public, and private sectors for the awareness and control of this ailment. In this regard, numerous brands are joining hands with Pink Ribbon Pakistan for raising awareness with the help of advocacy advertisements. This study aims to analyze some of the advocacy advertisements of Pakistan that were published online in October 2020. Using the lens of Hypermodality combined with Systemic Functional Grammar as presented by Halliday, and Visual Grammar given by Kress and Leeuwen, the researcher examines three advertisements to illustrate the way language, and visuals are being utilized by the advertisers. This study aims to articulate how, and why some of these advertisements are ineffective.

Keywords: Commodification, Breast cancer awareness, Pakistani advocacy advertisements

1. Introduction

Language, and images are an important part in formation and presentation of social reality and in a way bring changes by shaping attitudes and inculcating values. In recent times, visuals along with language are considered a communal method of correspondence that build real world through a conceptual as well as informal manner (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2006). Breast cancer happens to be the most frequent kind of tumour present in women as well as second highly prevalent tumour. Pink Ribbon Project is raising its awareness in various countries around the globe, and it came in Pakistan in 2004. Numerous brands collaborate and offer themselves for the cause to endorse consciousness about this ailment. Moreover, the month of October is observed as breast cancer awareness month and is also known as BCAM every year for the purpose of breast cancer awareness (Center, 2017). The campaigns utilize language, and images that spread awareness in terms of treating the disease. This gives rise to need of study of these advocacy advertisements from commodification perspective and the way language is being used by advertisers and brands, that is still absent in context of Pakistan. The studies conducted in Pakistan have worked on screening, treatment, and awareness about breast cancer in Pakistan (Firdous, 2017), identifying local beliefs and knowledge (Raza et al., 2012), knowledge about breast cancer and perceived barriers (Qasim et al., 2020), promotion of breast cancer awareness and clinical breast examination (Talib et al., 2019), role of BCA advertisements' educational messages in educating women (Iftikhar et al., 2019), and awareness among women regarding signs and screening (Siddique, 2017).

1.1. Objectives of the study

This study aims:

- To analyze and investigate the Pink Ribbon Project Pakistan and the role of language and visuals used in advocacy advertisements in raising awareness of cancer.
- To investigate the commodification of cause of Pink Ribbon Project by Pakistani national and international companies in their advertisements.

1.2. Research questions

The study aims find answers to the following research question:

- How far do the language and the accompanying visuals used in the Pakistani advocacy advertisements promote awareness of cancer?
- What is the extent to which the cause of Pink Ribbon Project has been commodified by Pakistani national and international companies in their advertisements?

2. Literature review

Breast cancer is the second most prevalent kind of cancer that results in death of majority of women (ACS, 2011; Jemal et al., 2010). Preliminary recognition of this ailment can prove to be impactful in decreasing the mortality rate of this ailment. In the preliminary detection, this disease is inspected based on results of the inspections of the breast cells with the help of microscope can later prove to be useful in analysing the scope of this disease as well as distinguish its pattern (ACS, 2013a; Khaliq et al., 2013).

The pink ribbon as breast cancer activism originated in 1992 when Charlotte Haley distributed peach-coloured ribbons (McCormick, 2009). Later the Self Magazine offered Haley a chance of getting the donation in return for the permission to use those ribbons, but the invitation was refused by Haley and so the Self Magazines used pink coloured ribbon as an emblem of breast cancer awareness (King, 2006).

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The situation of breast cancer is quite critical in Pakistan. One in every eight Pakistani women is fighting with this disease (Shaukat, 2020). One of the studies indicated that according to the data collected from Shaukat Khanum Memorial Cancer Hospital & Research Centre, Lahore in the year of 2016, the prevalent diagnosis among females turned out to be breast cancer which was almost 44.56% of the cancers. Similarly in the year 2017, once again this medical condition turned out to be the prominent one with almost 1244 instances.

A quantitative study conducted by Masood et al. (2016) in Bahawalpur concluded that vast majority of woman survey participants had inadequate awareness concerning this disease. There are many factors that are involved in delaying the treatment of this ailment. In study undertaken by Baig et al. (2018), the researchers identified the factors that were responsible for delayed treatment of cancer in Pakistan. One the factors for delayed treatment can be the lack of breast cancer awareness campaigns in Pakistan. A study done by Soomro (2017) analyzed the breast cancer awareness campaigns and concluded that the current techniques and strategies are not sufficient and so they need to be changed to bring the change. Women are often unaware of the methods to deal this ailment. A study done by Naz et al. (2016) analyzed how the women handle and manage this ailment. In addition to this, some other studies conducted in Pakistan have worked on screening, treatment, and awareness about breast cancer in Pakistan (Firdous, 2017), promotion of breast cancer awareness and clinical breast examination (Talib et al., 2019), role of educational messages of BCA advertisements in educating women (Iftikhar et al., 2019), and awareness among women regarding signs and screening (Siddique, 2017). All these studies have highlighted the need for measurements to be taken to enhance the treatments of cancer in Pakistan.

In the present times, various organizations use breast cancer awareness for marketing purposes. The advertisements concerning breast cancer use pink ribbon to show awareness as well as search for treatment of this ailment. The symbol can act as cue that is likely to change the mindset of consumers by developing a link between cause and the brand (Petty & Cacioppo, 1984; Andrews & Shimp, 1990).

Marx (1991) presented the concept of commodity as some lasting object invented by people. Moreover, the commodity must possess certain qualities for satisfying the need of people. Marx categorizes the commodity into use value and exchange value wherein both are needed by the object to be tagged as commodity (Marx et al., 1991). Use-value is understood as value assigned to a commodity due to its usage, whereas exchange-value is understood as value assigned due to exchange value of commodity.

Breast cancer awareness campaign became the center of attention with the rise of neoliberalism in different countries (King, 2006). Prevalent awareness campaigns are the reflection of neoliberal ideas where the sole responsibility of health is on the individual rather than on the state and all this depends upon the privatization of health-care developments for the treatment of this ailment (Gibson et al., 2014; Ness, 2014). In recent times, brands are frequently getting involved in awareness campaign of breast cancer (King, 2006). The breast cancer awareness campaign is being inappropriately used by various brands and this phenomenon is known as pinkwashing. Malkan (2007) identifies it as a process where the various companies present themselves as the ones that are playing their role to eradicate this ailment. Additionally, Casserly, Lubitow, and Davis (2011) describe it as an exercise where pink ribbon as well as pink color is used to indicate that the company has joined hands for the solution of this problem that can be often false when observed practically.

3. Methodology

The objective of the research is to carry out a comprehensive analysis of the advocacy advertisements (texts and images) advertised by various Pakistani national and international companies. The advertisements due to their breast cancer awareness and advocacy value, will follow a descriptive and qualitative model. The corpus comprises of three online advertisements collected and analyzed in accordance with the formulation of the problem and research objectives. The advertisements were collected randomly during the month of October 2020 also known as Breast Cancer Awareness month and later they were placed in three group based on textual analysis.

4. Theoretical framework

In the present study, the aim is to analyze advertisements published online by various brands, their language, and accompanying visuals. The online advertisements fall under the heading of hypertext owing to their linkage with other hypertexts present in them and so they can be analyzed by using Lemke's theory of Hypermodality (2002). The theory of Hypermodality provides a general overview of hypertext and the study requires in-depth analysis of language as well as accompanying visuals. To achieve the purpose of study, the researcher has used theory of commodification as proposed by Marx (1991), Lemke's theory of Hypermodality (2002), and Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar (2014) and Kress and Van Leeuwen's theory of Visual Grammar (2006) for the in-depth analysis of language as well as accompanying visuals.

4.1. Commodification

Marx (1991) presented the concept of commodity as some lasting object invented by people. Moreover, the commodity must possess certain qualities for satisfying the need of people. Marx categorizes the commodity into use value and exchange value wherein both are needed by the object to be tagged as commodity (Marx et al., 1991). Use-value is understood as value assigned to a commodity due to its usage, whereas exchange-value is understood as value

assigned due to exchange value of commodity. According to the commodification ideology, the value of any thing is only in terms of its monetary value and when health care is a commodity then it implies that it does not carry any other value or importance rather, it has value only in terms of money (based on Strasser, 2003). The ideology of commodification weakens the concept of medical facility as basic human need which in turn, emasculates the ethical objectives of medical professionals as well as professional morality (based on McCabe, 2004).

4.2. Hypermodality

As indicated by Lemke (2002), semiotics proposes the importance of three concurrent structures i.e., presentational, orientational, and organizational. These are the main speculations of different structures that Halliday (1978) gives about linguistic signs, which are practically considered as assets for the declaration of implications. Every content and picture have importance in show, bearing and association. These three summed up semiotic capacities are shared factors. Multimodal semiotics utilizes them to communicate the expected blended significance of increase.

4.3. Systemic Functional Grammar

Systemic Functional Grammar was introduced for the first time by Michael Halliday in the year of 1985 and it describes an entirely new approach to the study of grammar. This approach is fundamentally diverse from the conventional view wherein language represents a set of rules to define structures of grammar. From this viewpoint, language is a device used for articulating meaning. Hence, grammar is a device that can be used to generate meaning with the help of writing. According to Halliday (2014), whenever we utilize language, we are doing three things; we are representing the world (the ideational function of language), we are creating, approving, or interacting with the people with whom we communicate, and establishing relationships (the interpersonal function of language), and we are combining sentences and thoughts in a specific way to form a cohesive and coherent text (textual function of language).

4.4. Theory of Visual Grammar

Social visual semiotics follow the metafunctional hypothesis of Halliday (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004; 2014, Halliday, 1994; 2004), expecting that language achieves different metafunctions at the same time, to be specific experiential, interpersonal and textual metafunction. A similar theory has been proposed by Kress and Van Leeuwen (1996; 2006) for visual socio-semiotic assets, that have been named as representational, interactional as well as compositional meaning. Kress and Van Leeuwen accept the view that 'images, similar to every single representative mode, should meet different correspondence (and show) requirements to assume the part of a complete communicative framework' (2006, p. 41).

In the present study, the aim is to analyze advertisements, their language and accompanying visuals and can be achieved by using Lemke's theory of Hypermodality (2002) for analysis of advertisements as the online advertisements fall under the heading of hypertext due to linkage of text with other texts. The theory of Hypermodality provides a general overview of the hypertext. To get in-depth analysis of language, and images, we have used Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar (2014) and Kress and Van Leeuwen's theory of Visual Grammar (2006).

5. Analysis of the data

The present study will be carried out in three phases. The analysis of these advertisements will also be divided into three stages i.e., textual, visual, and hypermodal analysis.

Analysis of Case A: Advertisement providing awareness: Nishat Linen

The advertisement is by Nishat linen that presents the awareness about breast cancer. The text given in the advertisement can be interpreted as one encouraging the consumers to join hands for the treatment of this ailment.

The contents of the advertisement comprise of #SAVETHE9TH that associates this advertisement with campaign of Pink Ribbon Pakistan, textual description, and associated image of pink ribbon.

5.1. Textual analysis

According to Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar, the text can be analyzed at three different levels i.e., experiential analysis, mood analysis, and textual analysis.

5.1.1. Analysis of language using experiential analysis

There are 08 clauses in the advertisement. An overview of the advertisement's transitivity patterns reveals all clauses except one comprise of material process (see APPENDIX for SFG analysis). The advertiser has implied the use of the material and relational processes in the projection of this theme. The material process has been used to show it as an outward and actual struggle that is taking place in the real world and to indicate that patients are not alone. In the clause b, c, d, e, f, g, and h there is no actor that implies that according to advertiser either the actor is not so important, or he is trying to pay more attention to the action as compared to the actor.

5.1.2. Analysis of language using mood analysis

The advertisement is about the awareness of breast cancer and how we should join hands for its eradication. In the advertisement, the advertiser is the narrator who is suggesting the joint struggle for eradication of this ailment and due to this reason, it is like giving information about a happening, so 03 clauses are in the declarative mood and 05 clauses are in imperative mood. The advertiser has utilized imperative as well as declarative. The overall view of the advertisement is of inspirational due to imperative mood. The presence of imperative sentences makes it prominent and highlights the need for action and declaration for change. The advertiser has used the present form of finite to generate feeling of proximity and is thus making it as a universal phenomenon. The use of present tense has marked it as an ongoing struggle that is occurring in many parts of the world and is thus highlighting it as a universal fact.

5.1.3. Analysis of language using thematic analysis

The themes of advertisement were analyzed to get an overview of message being presented in the advertisement. There is no textual theme, that is connecting the clauses. The use of interpersonal theme implies that the advertiser is trying to develop a specific relationship of theme with the participants.

5.2. Visual analysis

According to the Kress and Leeuwen's model, we can analyze image at three levels i.e., representational, interactional, and compositional.

5.2.1. Analysis of image using representation function

In the advertisement, there is no participant, and this is a demonstration of symbolic attributive process. The pink ribbon is the symbolic attribute and is a symbol of breast cancer awareness. In this advertisement, it can be considered as an element that proves distinctiveness of brand as an awareness-raising brand. Therefore, it can be seen as the intention of advertiser to embody Nishat linen brand as raising awareness.

5.2.2. Analysis of image using interactional function

There is no participant in the advertisement so there is no gaze and likewise no social distance. The symbol in the advertisement has been depicted from the front side and this shows participation of spectators. It can also indicate that spectators are component of symbolic realm of breast cancer, and hence, it presents symbol and spectator from similar world. In the advertisement, there is low modality due to the absence of dynamic colours and presence of natural depth. On the other hand, the values of markers of modality are higher that further enhance the naturalistic view as well as modality. Due to these varying factors, the advertisement gives out different realism that is higher than normal. The advertiser using such realism suggests the idea of world of advertisements as achievable where the consumer can identify himself.

5.2.3. Analysis of image using compositional function

In this advertisement, the image comprises of mediator polarized image. The '*test yourself and save life*' are placed at the central position and acts as mediator between the given and new, and ideal and real information. The '*Nishat linen supports Pink Ribbon Pakistan*' is present in the upper part of image and indicate the ideal information. They visualize the promise of product and tends to make emotive appeal to the consumers.

The lower part is occupied by the '*save the 9th*', and it indicates real information and visualizes the product and provides practical information to the consumer. While '*Don't give up and get help*' are present on the left side and so they indicate given information. Whereas '*be brave and you are not alone*' are present on right side and indicate new information. The image gives the view that the patients, who used to fight this ailment in the past, are no longer alone. In the advertisement, the words '*Nishat linen*' have maximum salience whereas, the other text has relatively less salience. The text with the maximum salience is the foregrounded one and draws the attention of consumer towards it. It implies the idea that the advertisement revolves around the idea of breast cancer awareness.

5.3. Hypermodal analysis

According to Lemke's model, we can analyze hypertext at three different stages i.e., presentational, orientational, and organizational level to get meaning.

5.3.1. Presentational meaning

The advertisement has a simple composition. It comprises of pink ribbon that represents a connection with awareness campaign. The exhibited text as well as image present an analogous inner composition. In addition to this, there is

use of #SAVETHE9TH, that suggests a linkage among the various items of advertisement. With this prompt, we can interpret the advertisement as suggesting an effort for awareness of breast cancer.

5.3.2. Orientational meaning

The advertisement speaks to consumer textually with the help of imperatives and declaratives. Image comprises of hashtag of save the 9th and accompanying text. This advertisement has been designed for the viewers who are interested in this brand and care about their wellbeing. The text has been inviting people to join hands against this ailment, providing awareness regarding detection, and getting help to save their lives. The text changes the relationship between brand and viewers from consumers to partners working for the similar cause. Though the image and the text are different, but they have been interconnected with the idea of awareness.

5.3.3. Organizational meaning

The advertisement on the organizational level, creates a complicated connection. It presents offer and demand. The advertisement comprises of pink ribbon that symbolizes breast cancer awareness. The ribbon has replaced the 'I' in Nishat that presents the idea that Nishat linen has joined hands with Pink Ribbon Pakistan for the eradication of this ailment. The language, and the image in the advertisement are combined to present one unified meaning i.e., provision of breast cancer awareness. Similarly, the words 'Nishat linen' have maximum salience due to their size and so the eyes are automatically drawn to them. The salience of these words also highlights collaboration of brand with the cause i.e., breast cancer awareness. When we analyze the advertisement, then on the surface they may give different information but on deeper level they depict idea of provision of awareness to public about prevention of this ailment.

5.4. Overall interpretation

The advertisement presents the overview of breast cancer awareness and how this ailment can be eradicated. Overall, the advertisement revolves around the idea of breast cancer awareness, how fatality rates can be decreased and how the Nishat linen is playing its role in this awareness. The advertisement is providing awareness that early diagnosis can save life and is encouraging people to get tested. In this way, it is fulfilling the goals of Pink Ribbon Project. Based on this, we can conclude that advertisement is providing awareness.

Analysis of Case B: Advertisement providing hollow awareness: Daraz

The advertisement is by Daraz that presents the support for breast cancer. Corresponding text provided in the advertisement could be interpreted as one informing the customers about the month of October as BCAM. The contents of the advertisement comprise of tagline pink ribbon that acquaintances this advertisement with campaign of Pink Ribbon, textual explanation, and associated image.

5.5. Textual analysis

According to Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar, the text can be analyzed at three different levels i.e., experiential analysis, mood analysis, and textual analysis.

5.5.1. Analysis of language using experiential analysis

In the advertisement, there are 02 clauses. Transitivity patterns of this advertisement reveals that one of clauses (clause-b) comprises of relational process. Likewise, other clause (clause-a) comprises of material process (see APPENDIX for SFG analysis). In the clause a, the actor position is occupied by 'Daraz' that indicates it as a supportive brand. The advertisers have implied material process for the projection of theme of support. Advertiser has used the material process to show it as an outward and actual struggle that is taking place in the real world. The theme of awareness of regarding BCAM has been highlighted in clause b through use of relational processes for the description of this month.

5.5.2. Analysis of language using mood analysis

The advertisement is about the awareness of breast cancer month and support of brand. The advertiser is the narrator of this advertisement and is providing the information of month of October. The advertiser has utilized declarative sentences. The difference in subject finite structure forms different meanings, thus forming statements. The overall view of the advertisement is of narration due to declarative mood. The advertiser has used the present tense in the

advertisement to generate perception of proximity as well as anticipation. Present form of verb has been used to highlight the month of October as breast cancer awareness month, thus making it as a universal phenomenon.

5.5.3. Analysis of language using thematic analysis

These clauses have no textual themes so there is absence of connection between the clauses. The absence of interpersonal theme implies that the advertiser is not trying to develop a specific relationship of theme with participants. All these clauses aim to highlight the themes of breast cancer awareness present in advertisement. In the advertisement, the themes are marked. With the recurrent thematization in clauses, the advertiser shows his concern for breast cancer awareness.

5.6. Visual analysis

According to the Kress and Leeuwen's model, we can analyze image at three levels i.e., representational, interactional, and compositional.

5.6.1. Analysis of image using representation function

In the advertisement there is no participant, and it is demonstration of symbolic attributive process. The pink ribbon is the symbolic attribute and is a symbol of breast cancer awareness. In this advertisement, it can be considered as an element that proves distinctiveness of brand as an awareness-raising brand. Therefore, it can be seen as intention of advertiser to embody Daraz brand as raising awareness. Likewise, the description of BCAM is depicted in a circle and circles indicate warmth, safety as well as infinity. So, the use of circle implies that brand is trying to show its close connection with the cause.

5.6.2. Analysis of image using interactional function

This section will analyze the interactional meaning of advertisement that comprises of gaze, social distance, perspective, and modality of picture of advertisement. As there is no participant in the advertisement so there is no gaze and likewise no social distance. The advertisement has been depicted from the front side and this shows participation of spectators. It can also indicate that spectators are component of symbolic realm of Daraz and hence, it presents actor and spectator from similar world. In the advertisement, there is low modality due to the absence of dynamic colours and presence of natural depth. On the other hand, the values of markers of modality are higher that further enhance the naturalistic view and modality. Due to these varying factors, the advertisement gives out different realism that is higher than normal. The advertiser using such realism suggests the idea of world of advertisements as achievable where the consumer can identify himself.

5.6.3. Analysis of image using compositional function

The compositional meaning of the advertisement comprises of three elements i.e., information value, salience, and framing. In this advertisement, the image comprises of polarized image wherein the image is divided between the given and new information. The text '*Daraz cares*' is present on the left side and indicates the given information. In this case, it shows Daraz as acknowledged brand for caring. Likewise, the information regarding the month of October is present on the right side and indicates the new information. In the advertisement, the word '*Daraz*' has maximum salience and other text has relatively less salience. The text with the maximum salience implies the idea that the advertisement revolves around the idea of Daraz. Likewise, there is presence of frames in the image, and so there is maximum disconnection in the image. The disconnection in image, and salience indicate that advertisement is focused more on brand than on awareness.

5.7. Hypermodal analysis

According to Lemke's model, we can analyze hypertext at three different stages i.e., presentational, orientational, and organizational level to get meaning.

5.7.1. Presentational meaning

The advertisement has a simple composition. It comprises of text that says Daraz cares. In addition to this, there is use of tagline pink ribbon that suggests a linkage among various items of advertisement. Language, and symbol are presenting the connection of Daraz with awareness campaign wherein brand is trying to develop a relationship with campaign.

5.7.2. Orientational meaning

The advertisement when analyzed on orientational level refers to consumer with the help of declaratives. Image of advertisement comprises of awareness about BCAM and accompanying text. This advertisement has been designed for the viewers who are customers of Daraz and care about their wellbeing. The text has been telling people that it cares for breast cancer awareness, but no awareness is being provided in advertisement. Though the image and text are different, but they have been interconnected with the idea of awareness.

5.7.3. Organizational meaning

The advertisement on the organizational level, creates a complicated connection. The advertiser uses text to make a linkage between Daraz and BCAM. Likewise, the word '*Daraz*' has maximum salience due to its size and so the eyes are automatically drawn to it.

5.8. Overall interpretation

Apparently, the advertisement revolves around the idea of breast cancer awareness month but on a closer analysis we come to conclusion that advertiser is not providing any specific awareness in this advertisement. Rather, the advertiser is stating the general information to show its connection to the cause. The presence of frame and salience indicate that

advertisement is focused more on Daraz than on awareness, and the brand is trying to commodify the campaign of breast cancer awareness. The advertisement is providing view that firm is not providing any specific awareness rather they are only using this month as an opportunity to present themselves as awareness raising brand and so they are only providing hollow awareness that is of no use to consumers. Based on this, we can conclude that advertisement is providing hollow awareness.

Analysis of advertisement commodifying awareness campaign: Meezan bank

The advertisement is by Meezan bank that presents the awareness about breast cancer. The text given in the advertisement can be interpreted as one encouraging the consumers to fight against this ailment. The contents of the advertisement comprise of logo of bank, textual description, and image of ribbon. The text and image have been combined in a way to give an overview about awareness of breast cancer.

5.9. Textual analysis

According to Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar, the text can be analyzed at three different levels i.e., experiential analysis, mood analysis, and textual analysis.

5.9.1. Analysis of language using experiential analysis

There are 03 clauses in the advertisement. An overview of the advertisement's transitivity patterns reveals that one of clauses comprises of relational process. The other 02 clauses comprise of material process (see APPENDIX for SFG analysis). Advertiser has used the material process to show it as an outward and actual struggle that is taking place in the real world. In the clause a, there is no actor, and it implies the view that advertiser is focusing on fight against breast cancer rather than actors. The relational process has been used to develop relationship between October and breast cancer awareness month. The material processes show the activities, and how consumers should participate for awareness and relational process has been used for the description of the month of October. All the clauses and their constituents are highlighting the theme of awareness of breast cancer.

5.9.2. Analysis of language using mood analysis

The advertisement is about the awareness of breast cancer, and how we should join hands for its eradication. In the advertisement, the advertiser is the narrator who is suggesting the joint struggle for eradication of this ailment. Due to this reason, it is like giving information about a happening. The advertiser has utilized imperative, and declarative sentences. The presence of exclamative sentence makes it prominent and highlights the need for action and declaration for change. It shifts the mood of the advertisement from descriptive to inspirational.

5.9.3. Analysis of language using thematic analysis

These clauses have no textual themes, and so there is absence of connection between the clauses. The use of interpersonal theme implies that the advertiser is trying to develop a specific relationship of theme with the participants. All these clauses aim to highlight the theme of breast cancer awareness present in the advertisement.

5.10. Visual analysis

According to the Kress and Leeuwen's model, we can analyze image at three levels i.e., representational, interactional, and compositional.

5.10.1. Analysis of image using representation function

In the advertisement there is no participant, rather only a ribbon and therefore, this is a demonstration of symbolic attributive process. The pink ribbon is the symbolic attribute and is considered to be a symbol of breast cancer awareness.

On the contrary in this advertisement, the ribbon has depicted in purple colour to match the logo of brand. Purple ribbon is normally used as a symbol of hope for pancreatic patients but here the use of purple ribbon implies that the

brand is trying to commodify the cause as they have coloured the ribbon according to their own brand. It can be considered as an element that proves Meezan bank as commodifier of cause of breast cancer awareness.

5.10.2. Analysis of image using interactional function

There is no participant in the advertisement so, there is no gaze and likewise, no social distance. The symbol in the advertisement has been depicted from the front side and this shows participation of spectators. It can also indicate that spectators are component of symbolic realm of breast cancer, and hence, it presents actor as well as spectator from similar world.

In the advertisement, there is low modality due to the absence of dynamic colours, and presence of natural depth. On the other hand, the values of markers of modality are higher that further enhance the naturalistic view as well as modality. Due to these varying factors, the advertisement gives out different realism that is higher than normal. The advertiser by the use of such realism suggests the idea of world of advertisements as achievable where the consumer can identify himself.

5.10.3. Analysis of image using compositional function

In this advertisement, image comprises of mediator polarized image wherein the text i.e., '*Breast cancer, let's beat cancer together, October, and Breast cancer awareness month*' is placed at the central position and acts as mediator between the given and new, and ideal and real information. Likewise, the logo of bank is present in the left upper margin and indicates the ideal given information. It visualizes the promise of product and tends to make emotive appeal to the consumers.

In advertisement, the words '*breast/beat cancer*' have maximum salience and other text has relatively less salience. The text with the maximum salience implies the idea that the advertisement revolves around the idea of breast cancer. Likewise, there is absence of frames in the image, and the image is connected by similarities of colour. Due to these reasons, we can say that there is maximum connection in image. The image overall, revolves around the idea of fight against breast cancer. Whereas the use of purple ribbon indicates that the campaign is being commodified by advertiser.

5.11. Hypermodal analysis

According to Lemke's model, we can analyze hypertext at three different stages i.e., presentational, orientational, and organizational level to get meaning.

5.11.1. Presentational meaning

The advertisement has a simple composition. It comprises of purple coloured ribbon that represents a view that it is being commodified by the brand. There is use of ribbon that suggests a linkage among the various items of advertisement. Language and symbol are presenting the connection of Meezan bank with awareness campaign wherein brand is trying to commodify the cause to enhance its own sales.

5.11.2. Orientational meaning

The advertisement when analyzed on orientational level refers to consumer with the help of imperative and declarative sentences. The text has been inviting people to join hands against this ailment and it changes the relationship between brand and viewers from consumers to partners working for the similar cause. Though the image and the text are different, but they have been interconnected with the idea of awareness.

5.11.3. Organizational meaning

The advertisement on the organizational level, creates a complicated connection. It presents a demand. The advertisement comprises of purple ribbon that symbolizes campaign is being commodified by brand. It has changed the meaning of pink ribbon altogether as purple ribbon is symbol of hope for pancreatic patients.

Similarly, the words '*Breast/Beat Cancer*' have maximum salience due to their size and so the eyes are automatically drawn to them. When we analyze the advertisement then on the surface, they may give same idea that brand is extending its support for the cause. On deeper level it depicts the view that in advertisement the information being given to consumers is of no practical use. Therefore, we can call this as hollow awareness and assume that brand is pinkifying its advertisement by use of purple-coloured ribbon.

5.12. Overall interpretation

Apparently, it presents the overview of fight against breast cancer awareness but on a closer scrutiny, it shows that the campaign is being commodified by the brand. Instead of showing real support for the cause, the brand is using it for their own publicity. The advertisement is providing view that brand is not providing any specific awareness rather they are only using this month as an opportunity to pinkify their brand and so they are not taking any steps that are fulfilling the objectives of Pink Ribbon Pakistan. Based on this, we can conclude that advertisement is pinkifying the cause of breast cancer awareness to increase their potential consumers.

6. Discussion

6.1. Research question one

The language and accompanying visuals used in Pakistani advocacy advertisements are divided into three groups i.e., advertisements that are promoting awareness, those advertisements that are providing hollow awareness, and the advertisements that are only commodifying the cause. Analysis of advertisement that supports breast cancer awareness

show that the support of various Pakistani national and international brands is being extended for this cause. Various brands are using advertisement to support breast cancer awareness and raising their voice for its eradication. Analysis of advertisement that is providing hollow awareness show that all these advertisements are indicating that support of various Pakistani national and international brands is being extended for this cause yet on a closer analysis it was revealed that these advertisements are not providing any information or awareness that might be useful for viewers. On the contrary, they are providing hollow awareness in order to show their support of the cause. Various brands are using advertisement to order to increase their own sales by showing support for the cause.

Analysis of advertisement that is commodifying breast cancer awareness campaigns show that the advertisement is showing the commodification of this campaign by various Pakistani national and international brand as it is using pink ribbon in their advertisements to develop a link with the campaign and is neither taking steps for its eradication nor raising awareness. Rather, they are pinkifying their advertisement to attract their potential consumers.

To conclude, one of the selected advertisements is providing awareness whereas other two are trying to promote their own brands. The awareness being provided by these advertisements is limited and does not provide any information regarding the prevention and treatment of this ailment. In this way, language and the accompanying visuals used in the Pakistani advocacy advertisements are providing awareness of breast cancer that is limited to general information.

6.2. Research question two

In these advertisements, information that is being specified by awareness campaign is affected by resemblance of product with cause. This implies that a connection must be present between product and cause. Like women are mostly impacted by breast cancer and so the female products are more impactful in grabbing attention of female audience. Likewise, use of cause by the companies enhances brand image and changes preference of consumers. The existence of pink ribbon in the messages of cause-related marketing indicates connection between breast cancer awareness and brand. Such messages while using visual and verbal means provide information about cause and brand. These different elements influence behavior of consumer towards brands. The study highlights the fact that by constantly restating the components of breast cancer awareness, the different brands as well as their respective campaigns form a specific insight of this ailment. It results in awareness that highlights the general awareness and the information about prevention and treatment is withheld from the public. The awareness being provided in these advertisements is limited and does not encompass the debate of prevention and treatment.

The different advertisements are trying to spread awareness by using the perception of women being empowered and inspiring them to adapt and regulate their lives. This kind of advertising places consumers in a position to be responsible for their health and wellbeing by playing active role in detection of this ailment. Advertisement is using words like ‘early detection- early protection’ (Case A) and thus, the advertisers are shifting the whole responsibility of health and wellbeing on women. Such statements show responsibility being shifted to women as well as empowerment being given to them with that, they can make choices regarding their wellbeing. This kind of empowerment is often misleading owing to fact that consumers are being misguided by being provided the view that being healthy is their personal responsibility.

7. Conclusion

The analysis of advertisements showed that various advocacy advertisements are using the narrative of breast cancer awareness, but a closer scrutiny of these advertisements indicated that most of the advertisements are promoting their own brands instead of spreading awareness. The linguistic and visual analysis also indicated that breast cancer campaigns are being shaped by ideology of commodification that is working for the normalization of commodification of different aspects of life and places the responsibility of wellbeing on the individual. The advocacy advertisements by various Pakistani national and international companies are commodifying the cause of Pink Ribbon Project with the help of language and images used in them. The companies are spreading the rhetoric of responsibility and are thus shaping the minds of public in a way wherein the responsibility of health is being shifted from state to individual. They are using this ideology to increase the sales of their own products and are damaging the purpose of these awareness campaigns.

Appendix

Case A: Advertisements Raising Awareness: Nishat

a. Nishat linen supports Pink Ribbon Pakistan.

Transitivity analysis			
Nishtat linen	Supports	Pink Ribbon Pakistan	
Actor	Material process	Goal	
Interpersonal analysis			
Nishat linen	Supports		Pink Ribbon Pakistan
Subject	Finite	Predicate	Complement
Mood		Residue	
Textual analysis			
Nishat linen	Supports Pink Ribbon Pakistan		
Theme	Rheme		

b. Don't give up.

Transitivity analysis	
Don't	give up
Material process	Goal
Interpersonal analysis	
Don't	
Finite	give up
Mood	Complement
Residue	
Textual analysis	
Don't give	
Theme	Up
Rheme	

c. Test yourself.

Transitivity analysis	
Test	yourself
Material process	Goal
Interpersonal analysis	
Test	
Finite	yourself
Mood	Complement
Residue	
Textual analysis	
Test	
Theme	Yourself
Rheme	

d. Be brave.

Transitivity analysis	
Be	Brave
Material process	Goal
Interpersonal analysis	
Be	
Finite	Brave
Mood	Complement
Residue	
Textual analysis	
Be	
Theme	Brave
Rheme	

e. Get help.

Transitivity analysis	
Get	Help
Material process	Goal
Interpersonal analysis	
Get	
Finite	Help
Mood	Complement
Residue	
Textual analysis	
Get	
Theme	Help
Rheme	

f. Save life.

Transitivity analysis	
Save	Life
Material process	Goal
Interpersonal analysis	
Save	
Finite	Life
Mood	Complement
Residue	
Textual analysis	
Save	
Life	

Theme	Rheme
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g. You are not alone.

Transitivity analysis		
You	Are	Not alone
Token	Relational process	Value
Interpersonal analysis		
You	Are	Not alone
Subject	Finite Predicate	Complement
Mood	Residue	
Textual analysis		
You	Are not alone	
Theme	Rheme	

h. Save the 9th.

Transitivity analysis		
Save	The 9 th	
Material process	Goal	
Interpersonal analysis		
Save	The 9 th	
Finite	Predicate	Complement
Mood	Residue	
Textual analysis		
Save	The 9 th	
Theme	Rheme	

Case B: Advertisement Raising Hollow Awareness: Daraz

a. Daraz cares

Transitivity analysis		
Daraz	Cares	
Actor	Material process	
Interpersonal analysis		
Daraz	Cares	
Subject	Finite	Predicate
Mood	Residue	
Textual analysis		
Daraz	Cares	
Theme	Rheme	

b. Breast cancer awareness month October

Transitivity analysis		
Breast cancer awareness month	October	
Attribute	Carrier	
Interpersonal analysis		
Breast cancer awareness month	October	
Subject	Complement	
Mood	Residue	
Textual analysis		
Breast cancer awareness month	October	
Theme	Rheme	

Case C: Advertisement Commodifying Campaign: Meezan

a. Beat cancer.

Transitivity analysis		
Beat	Cancer	
Material process	Goal	
Interpersonal analysis		
Beat	Cancer	

Finite	Predicate	Complement
Mood	Residue	
Textual analysis		
Beat cancer		
Theme		

b. Let's beat cancer together.

Transitivity analysis					
Let's	Beat		Cancer	Together	
Actor	Material process		Goal	Circumstance	
Interpersonal analysis					
Let	Us	Beat		Cancer	Together
Adjunct	Subject	Finite	Predicate	Complement	Adjunct
Re-	Mood		-esidue		
Textual analysis					
Let's	Beat cancer together				
Theme	Rheme				

c. October Breast cancer awareness month

Transitivity analysis			
October		Breast cancer awareness month	
Carrier		Attribute	
Interpersonal analysis			
October		Breast cancer awareness month	
Subject		Complement	
Mood		Residue	
Textual analysis			
October		Breast cancer awareness month	
Theme		Rheme	

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